

EXTRACELLULAR BIOSYNTHESIS OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES BY *BACILLUS TROPICUS* ISOLATED FROM HEAVY METAL CONTAMINATED SOIL

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Article Received on 05 Dec. 2025,
Article Revised on 25 Dec. 2025,
Article Published on 05 Jan. 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18219597>

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How to cite this Article: Sayali Patil*¹, Dilip Kadam² (2026). EXTRACELLULAR BIOSYNTHESIS OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES BY *BACILLUS TROPICUS* ISOLATED FROM HEAVY METAL CONTAMINATED SOIL. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(1), 1002–1008.

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ABSTRACT

Recently silver nanoparticles are subject of extensive research because of their exceptional physical, chemical, biological characteristics. Silver nanoparticles are found to possess potential uses in variety of fields including medical, environmental, agriculture and human health. Extracellular synthesis of silver nanoparticles is more convenient due to comparatively easy recovery process. Further, the product is obtained in more in quantity and pure form. In the present study silver nanoparticles were synthesized by using bacterial isolates isolated from heavy metal contaminating soil. Total eight bacterial isolates were isolated and studied for their ability to synthesize silver nanoparticles extracellularly. The most efficient isolate was identified to be *Bacillus tropicus* based on 16S rRNA genome sequencing. Nanoparticle sample was characterized by using SEM, TEM and FTIR spectroscopy. The silver nanoparticle size was in the range between 50- 80 nm.

KEYWORDS: *Bacillus tropicus*, Silver nanoparticles, Extracellular synthesis, contaminated soil.

INTRODUCTION

The field of nanotechnology, which encompasses the synthesis and use of nanomaterials, is expanding rapidly and has important applications across diverse sectors. Silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) are characterized as silver particles that possess size in the range of 10-100 nm.^[1] Silver nanoparticles possess distinctive chemical and physical properties that have increased

interest from researchers across various fields globally. Currently, researchers demonstrate promising applications in areas such as medicine, agriculture, environmental remediation, food technology, and water treatment. The dimensions and configuration of nanoparticles can also be manipulated during microbial synthesis. Therefore, it is crucial to explore previously unstudied microorganisms for their ability to synthesize AgNPs.^[2] Biological synthesis of nanoparticles is more economic and eco-friendly. Microbial synthesis of silver nanoparticles can be done by intracellular or extracellular mode. The production of nanoparticles within cells necessitates extra procedures, like ultrasound treatment or interactions with appropriate detergents, to extract the produced nanoparticles. Conversely, the biosynthesis occurring outside of cells is cost-effective and involves less complicated processing after synthesis. This advantage supports the large-scale manufacturing of silver nanoparticles to investigate their possible applications. Hence researchers are interested for the study of silver nanoparticles.

Prolonged and ongoing interactions between microbes and different metals are likely to occur among bacterial isolates sourced from industrialized regions. This enhances the likelihood of discovering unique microbial strains that possess the ability to form nanoparticles.^[2] In the current study bacteria were screened from heavy metal contaminated soil collected from Karad Projects Ltd. Karad. The latitude of Karad, India is 17.286501, and the longitude is 74.181427 located in Satara District in Maharashtra. The Selected bacterial strain was identified as *Bacillus tropicus*.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Soil samples were collected from heavy metal contaminated soil from Karad Projects Ltd. Karad. Total 1g of soil sample was inoculated in 100 ml sterile Nutrient broth containing 1.0 mM conc. of AgNO₃ and incubated for 24 h at room temperature for enrichment of silver nitrate resistant bacteria. 0.1 ml amount of enriched broth was inoculated on sterile nutrient agar containing 1.0 mM concentration of AgNO₃ and plates were incubated at room temperature for 48h. One of the potent isolates was selected for further study. The efficiency of isolates for silver nanoparticle synthesis was checked by checking absorbance of nanoparticle solution by UV visible spectroscopy. Isolated strain was identified by 16S rRNA sequencing. The Strain was identified as *Bacillus tropicus*.

Synthesis of silver nanoparticles

For synthesis of silver nanoparticles 1 ml culture was inoculated in 1000 ml sterile nutrient broth and incubated in shaker at 150 rpm for 24 h. The broth was then centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 min. The pellet was then transferred in sterile distilled water in flask and incubated in shaker at 150 rpm for 24 h. After incubation the solution was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 10 min. The pellet discarded and supernatant transferred in a separate flask. 1.0 mm of AgNO₃ were added in supernatant and kept in sunlight. The colorless supernatant turned into dark brown color within few minutes. Extraction of silver nanoparticles was done by centrifugation of the solution at 10000 rpm for 10 min. The pellet was transferred in evaporating dish and dried at 60⁰c to powder form of silver nanoparticles that was then characterized by different tests.

Characterization of silver nanoparticles

The optical properties of the synthesized silver nanoparticles were examined by using a UV–Vis spectrophotometer. In this process, samples containing nanoparticles underwent absorption analysis over a wavelength range of 300–700 nm with the UV–Vis spectrophotometer. Nanoparticle sample characterization was then done by SEM and TEM analysis to know the size of particles. FTIR analysis was also done to check functional groups present in compound.

RESULT

Total eight isolates showing extracellular nanoparticle synthesis ability were isolated. After checking of their efficiency for nanoparticle synthesis by UV visible spectroscopy; N4 isolate that showed sharp peak at 420 nm wavelength was selected for further studies. Bacterial genomic DNA identification was done by Sanger's sequencing (16S rRNA sequencing) method and the isolate was identified as *Bacillus tropicus*. Biosynthesis of nanoparticles visualized by change in solution color. The colorless supernatant turned to dark brown color within few minutes [figure1]. Synthesized nanoparticle sample was subjected to UV visible spectra of nanoparticle sample showed peak at 420 nm [figure 2]. To check functional group FTIR analysis carried out. FTIR spectra shown in figure 3. FTIR analysis showed peak at single bond and double bond region and also in fingerprint region. According to graph peak at 1621 cm⁻¹ shows presence of alkenyl (C=C) group. Peak at 1556 cm⁻¹ shows presence of aliphatic nitro compounds. Peak at 1394, 1454, 1335 cm⁻¹ showed presence of trimethyl,

methylene and methyne groups respectively.^[3] Particles shape and size was characterized by SEM and TEM analysis that showed 50 nm size range [figure 4 and figure 5] respectively.

Figure 1: (a) Before addition of AgNO₃ to CFE (b) After addition of AgNO₃ to CFE.

Figure 2: UV visible spectra of nanoparticle shows 420 nm wavelength.

Figure 3: FTIR analysis of N4 nanoparticle sample.

Figure 4: SEM image.

Figure 5: TEM image.

DISCUSSION

Biogenic synthesis of silver nanoparticles is ecofriendly, cost effective method. Bacteria can synthesize intracellularly and extracellularly. *Bacillus tropicus* strain isolated from heavy

metal contaminated soil shown in extracellular synthesis of silver nanoparticles. Synthesis of silver nanoparticles done by using cell free extract method.^[1] Synthesis was observed by change in color from colorless to dark brown.^[2] UV visible spectroscopic analysis showed peak at 420 nm closely similar results shown by *Bacillus licheniformis*.^[4] Synthesized nanoparticles can be used for application as antifungal substance.^[1] Silver nanoparticles also have significant application in dye degradation.^[5] As compare to these results *Bacillus tropicus* silver nanoparticles solution shown a UV absorption peak at 420 nm and size about 50 nm.

CONCLUSION

The results of the present study showed the bacterial isolate that was identified as *Bacillus tropicus* possess ability of extracellular biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles. UV visible spectrum showed peak at 420 nm confirmed presence of silver nanoparticles in solution. FTIR, SEM and TEM analysis showed the presence of about 50 nm to 80 nm size silver nanoparticles. This study successfully reports extracellular biosynthesis of silver nanoparticles produced by *Bacillus tropicus*. The extracellular synthesized silver nanoparticles can be used for environmental remediation like textile dye degradation or in other fields.

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